

Overcoming Language Interference in Teaching English to Adult Students in the System of Further Education

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Abstract: *The article deals with the problem of teaching English to adult students in the system of further education. One of the barriers of forming English-speaking competence is language interference. The author outlines the ways of overcoming language interference while teaching English to adult students in the system of further education.*

Keywords: *language interference; adult students; teaching English; system of further education; ways of overcoming language interference.*

Introduction

A distinctive feature of a modern specialist is knowledge of a foreign language, which allows them to have a competitive advantage in the labor market. Currently, one of the most common foreign languages is English, which is due to both geopolitical and purely economic reasons. The need to satisfy the social demand for learning English has led to the emergence of a wide network of educational institutions of additional education that provide the opportunity to study English. The author's experience in such institutions 350 shows that adult learners have a sufficient level of motivation to master English. They clearly understand the purpose of learning English. Secondly, training in institutions of additional education is carried out on a fee-paying basis, which requires students to take a responsible approach to the educational process. At the same time, one of the barriers to learning English by adults, which makes the task of overcoming language interference in the process of teaching adults English especially relevant.

Materials.

The purpose of this publication is to highlight ways to overcome language interference in the process of teaching adults English in the additional education system. When starting to study English, adult students already have a certain set of knowledge about the language. Often this knowledge "conflicts" with the norms and principles of functioning of the language being studied. In this case, the above-mentioned phenomenon of language interference arises. It should be said that this phenomenon has become an object of research by scientists in various fields of scientific knowledge. Thus, in psychology, interference is understood as an inhibitory interaction of skills, in which already established skills hinder the formation of new ones or reduce their effectiveness [1, p. 461]. Despite the significant number of definitions of the concept of "language interference", researchers agree that language interference is a deviation from the speech norm of the second language, arising under the influence of the first language. Thus, A. S. Krutoberezhskaya considers language interference as "... cases of deviation from the speech norm that arise in the speech of a bilingual in a second (foreign) language under the influence of the first language" [2, p. 54]. In our opinion, language interference should be understood as the result of mixing language codes that occurs in the speech activity of students and affects the process of learning English.

Research and methods.

Experience in teaching English has allowed us to identify the factors that cause language interference, which include: - the influence of the native language of students;

- the influence of a second foreign language (often students studying in the system of additional education study a second foreign language or studied another foreign language at school); - socio-political, economic and cultural changes;
- the development of scientific thought;
- the presence of various standards of the English language.

Overcoming language interference involves determining the structure of this phenomenon. We believe that the structure of language interference corresponds to the levels of language. We share the opinion of M. P. Kochergan that the main levels of language include the phonological, morphological, lexical-semantic and syntactic levels [3, p. 213]. Mastering the English language involves studying the culture of English-speaking countries. As V. S. Vinogradov rightly notes, culture is a set of material and spiritual values accumulated and being accumulated by a certain community of people, and those values of one national community that are completely absent from another or differ significantly from them constitute the national socio-cultural fund that requires study in the process of learning a foreign language [4, p. 37]. Accordingly, we believe that language interference has the following structure:

- phonetic interference (mixing the phonetic rules of the English language and the rules of the native or first foreign language)

- grammatical interference (replacing the rules and features of the morphology of the English language with the rules of another language);
- lexical interference (representation of the concept being studied by means of the native or first foreign language);
- syntactic interference (transferring the rules of syntactic connection of another language to English);
- cultural interference (explanation of the phenomena of English-language culture by means of familiar cultural stereotypes).

Discussion.

A special feature of teaching English in the system of additional education is a practice-oriented approach to the organization of the educational process. In other words, the theoretical component of the learning process should be minimized as much as possible (but not to the detriment of understanding!), and most of the time should be devoted to the practical development of speech skills and abilities. Accordingly, in working with students, we practice creative phonetic tasks. When working in pairs, students must compose dialogues containing the phonetic material being studied. Another type of task is composing a story, when each student must come up with a continuation of the story, and the sentence must include the phonetic material being studied. As a rule, such tasks are positively perceived by students and contribute to better assimilation of the material. Thus, the ways to overcome linguistic interference of adult students are:

- using jokes or funny situations from teaching experience in the educational process;
- establishing associative links between a phoneme, its graphic representation and pronunciation;
- using creative phonetic tasks. An integral part of teaching a foreign language is teaching grammar. Based on the experience of teaching English in the system of additional education, we can conclude that the greatest difficulties for adult students are caused by learning the grammatical features of the English language. We see the reason for this in the significant differences in the grammatical structure of the native and English languages (the presence of articles, linking verbs, tenses in English, etc.).

Result. We see a way to overcome language interference at the grammar level in the systematization of grammatical features of the English language by creating algorithms. The effectiveness of this method is dictated, in our opinion, by a number of reasons.

Firstly, at the initial stage of language learning, students can rely on the algorithm until the skills are brought to automatism.

Secondly, the algorithm reflects the conditions of use of the grammatical phenomenon being studied, as well as exceptions to the rule. According to L. P. Kashirina, the potential of algorithms in teaching grammar of a foreign language is due to the possibility of reducing grammar to a finite set of rules [6, p. 46]. It is important that students also act as active participants in the creation of the algorithm, and not as simple “consumers of knowledge”. Presentation and consolidation of grammatical material also include visualization of the grammatical phenomenon through the use of pictures or dramatization and the development of the material in small educational forms, i.e. small texts containing the grammatical phenomenon being studied.

Conclusion. A key requirement for the personality of a modern specialist is proficiency in a foreign language as a means of international communication. English remains one of the most popular languages for learning foreign languages. Satisfaction of social demand determines the development of a system of additional education, where adult learners can master English to achieve both personal and professional goals. The author's experience in institutions of additional education has shown that adult learners often face the problem of language interference, which is based on the transfer of linguistic norms of the native (first foreign) language to English. As practice shows, the most effective ways to overcome language interference are:

1. the use of jokes or funny situations in the educational process from the teacher's experience, allowing you to create a positive atmosphere in the classroom and remove psychological barriers that adult students may experience;
2. the establishment of associative links that contribute to a more solid assimilation of the English language;
3. the use of creative language tasks that provide an opportunity for the practical implementation of the material studied;
4. algorithmization of educational material, allowing to systematize educational material and serving as a certain reference point for students (especially at the initial stage of learning English);
5. visualization of the material being studied, promoting solid assimilation of new lexical units and grammatical constructions;
6. use of tasks for practicing speech skills (drill exercises), the implementation of which allows to bring the formed speech skills to automatism;
7. correlation of the phenomenon being studied with the context of the utterance, which makes it possible to identify the essence and characteristics of the phenomenon;
8. introduction of a cultural component into the process of teaching English, allowing to overcome cultural differences and promoting a full and deep understanding of the culture of English-speaking countries as a reflection of the peculiarities of the development and functioning of the English language.

Of course, the material of the article does not exhaust all aspects of the problem under study. We see prospects for scientific research in the development of a modern teaching and methodological kit for teaching adults English in institutions of additional education.

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